

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE OF THE STUDENT

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Abstract: The theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of the physical culture of university students are methodological approaches that ensure the interdependence and integrity of the process, principles that reflect the content and characteristics of the approaches. The field of categorical research on the formation of physical culture of a university student includes the justification of the content of the concepts of "personal physical culture", "physical culture", "physical culture and valeological competence". The process of forming the physical culture of university students is effective if it is built on the following principles: a unity of systematic, cultural, activity-based, competence-based, innovative and student-oriented approaches to the formation of physical education. physical culture of the student; innovativeness of goal setting and its formation. The systematic approach serves as a methodological strategy in the formation of the physical culture of the student, and other approaches are combined with it. In the process of scientific work, a theoretical and methodological model of the formation of the physical culture of the student was developed.

Key words: physical culture of the student's personality, theoretical and methodological foundations, methodological, approaches, principles, model.

The transition of society to a new historical state, which determines objective changes in the development of humanity, objectively requires a radical new organization of such an important field as the education system, which is responsible for preparing a person for life and forming his cultural potential. It is not about any corrections, not about introducing new things, but about changing education, forming new principles, conditions, forms of its organization - subject, structural, semantic. Thus, one of the most important directions is the need to make radical changes to its existing content, which in most cases is not required by children either in school or after school life. [10].

Modern high school is aimed at forming a sufficiently qualified specialist competence. The reconstruction of the educational system set the task of future professional training and improvement of physical education and valeological activities before higher educational institutions.

specialists. Within the framework of the formation of a new paradigm of higher professional education, the issues of ensuring the social adaptation of the student to the changing life conditions, and the formation of a mentally and physically healthy specialist are gaining urgent importance. The formulation of these questions is especially related to the changed value orientations of the social system and the reconsideration of activities in all spheres of social and individual life, where the physical culture of a person occupies one of the

main places.

It is important that the formation of the physical culture of a university student's personality allows solving one of the problems facing the school, that is, the formation of a physically developed person who is able to fully and comprehensively implement his future professional activities.

In the current conditions of professional pedagogical education, a contradiction is revealed between large-scale scientific research in the field of physical culture, self-improvement of training specialists, and insufficient development of the theoretical and methodological foundations of physical culture formation. the student's personality.

The above determines the social importance and relevance of the selected research topic, the problem of which is formulated as follows: "what are the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of physical culture of the student".

The purpose of the research: to determine and justify the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of the physical culture of the student.

Materials and research methods

The analysis of scientific ideas about the formation of physical culture of the person made it possible to determine the main directions of knowledge in the field of physical culture in accordance with the purpose of our research: pedagogical,

psychological, sociological, medical-biological, professional-integrative, philosophical and cultural studies. In each of these research areas of physical culture, a tendency to eliminate the fragmentation of knowledge in solving interdisciplinary problems of modern science has been identified. [6]. The historical-pedagogical analysis of the process of formation of personal physical culture in educational institutions revealed the essence and trends of studying this problem, that is, physical culture and valeological education are becoming more interdisciplinary every decade. a gradual realization of the wholeness of man began to manifest itself more and more. The main trend of scientific works studied in the field of physical culture in higher educational institutions was determined, which is the transition to understanding the physical culture of a person as a necessary professional and personal person.

Characteristics of the future specialist from personal to professional-personal.

The study found that the interdisciplinary interaction of different academic subjects is necessary for the effective formation of the physical culture of the young generation [9].

At the level of a person, physical culture is part of the general structure of a person along with intellectual, worldview, aesthetic, moral and communicative culture: its formation should be supported by a specially oriented system of cultural innovative education.

Physical culture at the professional and personal level is a system of values that regulates professional activity; condition, purpose, method, means, level of professional activity

self-awareness in it, its result and evaluation criteria; the collective expression of the professional personality, the process of creating the world of culture in itself, the personal actualization of individual, unique meanings in it.

Learning means the process of forming a person's physical culture, managing its formation and development; a specially organized and purposeful process of diagnosis, design, practical implementation and monitoring of the formation of physical culture as a priority direction of personal development and professional training of students based on the

systematic use of modern science concepts; updated physical culture and wellness resources of pedagogical education in the academic, professional and extracurricular activities of students. In turn, the formation of physical culture of the personality of students of higher educational institutions, as a professional-personal quality of a specialist, should be carried out continuously from the first to the fifth year during specially organized trainings using the methodology of formation of physical culture. personal culture and its components: physical culture, psycho-physical training and physical culture - valeological competence [3].

Physical culture is one of the components of human physical culture, which includes:

- the world view of physical culture aimed at realizing the priority of physical culture with other types of personal culture;
- a motivational and value-based attitude to physical education and lifestyle is formed;
- ethics of physical education - a single normative-value set of ideas about the basics of physical exercises and physical education activities.

Psycho-physical preparation is a part of professional preparation for future teaching activities and is formed by

A certain complex is important

Important professional qualities for the psycho-physical development of a person. It serves as the main component of the student's physical culture in terms of ensuring the unity of professional and personal training for teaching work. The content of the future teacher's psycho-physical training is manifested in the optimal development of the psycho-physical qualities of the person and maintenance of physical culture and lifestyle.

Physical culture and valeological competence are the main components of human physical culture. This is an integral personal characteristic of the future teacher, which ensures the success of creative activity in standard and extraordinary pedagogical situations. It includes: readiness for professional self-improvement; productivity

Thinking and activity of physical culture; the ability to find new tools and methods of solving professional-pedagogical problems in the field of physical education and physical education and lifestyle, the ability to competently support physical culture and valeological self-development.

Students, readiness for creative physical culture and wellness activities in future professional activities.

Thus, the physical culture of a student's personality should be characterized as a professional and personal quality of a future specialist: 1) a worldview of physical education and a motivational-value attitude to physical activity; 2) optimal level of psycho-physical preparation for future professional activity; 3) physical education and valeological competence, including physical education.

Valeological knowledge and their moral implementation in the physical culture and lifestyle, in the process of mastering the physical culture of society and creating it.

The choice of approach and principles to the formation of the physical culture of a student's personality in a humanitarian university is determined by the desire to comprehensively reveal the essence of this process, which helps to achieve an integrative result - development. from the student's personality. Summarizing approaches to pedagogical design, we consider increasing the level of physical culture of a specialist as a systematic step-by-step process. The identified changes of priority in the values and goals of professional education prompted us to compare and choose methodological approaches to its

implementation that ensure the interdependence of the components of the model and the integrity of the process: systematic, innovative, student-oriented, activity-based, Cultural, competency-based and systemic innovation approaches.

The systematic approach is aimed at studying the formation of the physical culture of university students as a system, helps to reveal its integrity and allows to analyze its structural features and quality features. A systematic approach allows to manage the step-by-step process of forming the physical culture of a student's personality in the pedagogical space of a humanitarian university.

The ideas of the systematic approach occupy a leading position in various fields of science. In modern scientific literature, the systematic approach is often considered as a direction of socio-scientific knowledge and methodology of social practice based on the study of objects as integrated systems. A systematic approach helps to set problems in specific subjects and develop a strategy for studying them. The methodological specification of the systematic approach comes from the fact that it aims to reveal the integrity of the object and the mechanisms that ensure it, to identify different types of communication of the object and to combine them into a single theoretical picture.

It should also be noted that the systematic approach does not appear in the research process in its pure form, separated from other principles, ideas and approaches. Therefore, in our research, the systematic approach is complemented by other methodological ideas. The principles of a systematic approach are complemented by innovative, person-centered ideas.

Activity, cultural and other methodological approaches.

Analysis of philosophical and pedagogical literature (P.K. Anokhin, V.G. Afanasyev, A.N. Averyanov, V.A. Antyukhova, V.P. Bespalko, B.P. Bitinas, I.V. Blauberg, B.S. Gershunsky, V.V. Guzeev, M.A. Korjееv, F.A. Korjev, M.A.V. .V. Lomov, L.I. Novikova Yu.P. .Sokolnikov, A.V.Tutolmin, E.G.Yudin, etc.) allowed us to conclude that the systematic approach is unique in its use by various disciplines in knowing and changing reality. A systematic approach and its implementation in the field of education and training appear before us as a dialectical unity of general, private and individual. In order to understand the essence of a systematic approach to education, according to Yu.P. Sokolnikov, the presence of three aspects in the knowledge of the phenomena of the surrounding reality is of fundamental importance. It is the knowledge of the phenomenon taken by itself; to consider the event in a specific system, subject to its laws; to consider the phenomenon and its laws as a product of the entire complex of existing internal and external conditions. Based on these positions, the real picture of education in society is "a complex reality represented by many types of objects (systems) and their interaction" [8].

The analyzes show that at the beginning of the 21st century, there was a need for wide scientific and practical application of the ideas of a systematic approach to the consideration of complex objects, their design and improvement. This is largely due to the need to study the complex multidimensional objects of reality - from knowledge of the world of things and phenomena to knowledge of the world of systems. due to the fact that their patterns are trends in modern scientific research.

Physical culture of the person

from the point of view of the systematic approach, that is, the general scientific principle of studying pedagogical phenomena, that is, the quality of the system is considered as a subsystem of professional training, as a general order system. The determined

components of a person's physical culture form an organic unit, in which the organizing factor is professional and personal readiness for future activities. The dissertation shows that the components of the physical culture of the student's personality, as well as their structural elements, are closely related to each other, harmonize with each other and form a certain unity. Integrity

In the pedagogical space of a humanitarian university, the functioning of the physical culture of a student's personality is confirmed by the interaction of components and, accordingly, their components.

A systematic approach provides a holistic view of the physical culture of a person as a pedagogical phenomenon and a professional-personal characteristic. The future teacher aims at the unity of theory, experience and practice in this process of learning and change, to which his pedagogical training is interrelated and interrelated. allows building as a system of components.

The activity approach allows to reveal the meaningful and operational aspects of the formation of the physical culture of the personality of university students; considers education and upbringing as a system of certain types of activities, the implementation of which leads to fundamental knowledge and motivation among university students based on various forms of future professional activity.

The leading idea of the activity approach in our research is that the student is a subject of activity, and in the process of its implementation, he forms the physical culture of a person, taking into account individual characteristics and important personal needs.

By presenting the structure of activity, this approach allows to establish causal relationships at different levels of physical culture and valeological activity and to understand the nature of the events that determine the characteristics of culture formation. In addition, the activity approach explains the process of active acquisition of knowledge and skills through motivated and goal-oriented problem solving. The use of the activity approach in our research made it possible to reveal the content of the conceptual model of the formation of human physical culture.

The principle of purposeful stimulation of the student's physical education activities. The essence of this principle, which ensures the formation of a person's physical culture, is the implementation of a person's hereditary need for movement, self-improvement and further physical self-development based on the formed stable motivation. on creating an individual program of physical lifestyle. This principle is based on the achievement of the highest level of physical culture of a person and focuses on the individual characteristics, needs and motives of a person. In addition, the principle of purposeful encouragement of students to physical activity includes active pedagogical support in the formation of physical culture of the individual based on equal subject relations.

The principle of reflection as a thinking mechanism in the process of forming the physical culture of the student's personality. The formation of the physical culture of the student's personality is carried out on the basis of the principle of thinking, because the student's ability to think about his psycho-physical condition, behavior and attitudes, and in general the object of self-review (analysis and evaluation) and practical transformation. This principle envisions a pattern based on personal (the ability to reason, make decisions, and take responsibility for one's own choices) and activity (acquiring skills and strategies for physical education and recreation) development. shows.activity) parameters of autonomy [5].

A person-oriented approach is a theoretical and methodological basis for modeling the educational process, which ensures the supremacy of the individual over all professional training, self-education, self-education, self- z-allows you to create conditions for the development of self-education. , self-development in physical education, self-determination, independence and self-awareness, it is the psycho-physical capabilities of students based on their level of training, abilities and psycho-physiological personality of the student. allows for fuller manifestation according to its characteristics. It allows formation and practical implementation of the orientation of the process of training specialists to the personal development of the physical culture of a person. In the conditions of student-oriented education, physical education activities are managed by the teacher, taking into account the psycho-physical characteristics of students and their own capabilities. Professional training ensures personal development and freedom of students' ways of self-realization in the pedagogical space. The person-oriented approach is to define the humanitarian direction of professional training as an integral set of views, beliefs, ideals, where the individual is the highest value. The process of forming a student's physical culture achieves its goal, because it creates a situation of demand for personal forces of self-development.

The principle of content variability. Its implementation means choosing individual forms, methods and tools of education based on the specific characteristics of the educational and educational situation, ensuring the activity of students, forming the opportunity and need to build their own personal direction in them. requires. physical education activities.

In the logic of the cultural approach, various aspects of human essence as a subject of culture - worldview, consciousness, self-awareness, spirituality, ethics, creativity, ability to learn, etc. - not predicted by any model or theory, but understood as aspects of a holistic cultural personality. The approach of cultural studies makes it possible to consider the formation of physical culture as a component of culture as professional training on a broad general cultural basis, which is the leading regulator of the student's life activity, an indicator of professional and personal development. From this point of view, the formation of the physical culture of the student's personality is perceived through the prism of culture, i.e. as a process carried out in a culturally appropriate pedagogical space and imbued with personal and value meanings.

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